

IMPLEMENTATION OF GENDER RELATIONS IN DISCOURSE ANALYSIS

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Annotation: Language and gender studies are increasingly becoming gendered and discursive. The study of speech and gender is an interdisciplinary work of scholars in linguistics, anthropology, speech communication, social psychology, education, literature, and other disciplines. Many researchers have been primarily concerned with documenting gendered patterns of language use, but the field of language research has also covered many areas in which social and political aspects of gender relations can be seen.

Key words: gender and discourse, gender duality, language studies, social construction of gender, female language, concept of gender discourse, gender relations.

INTRODUCTION Speech and Gender Studies Linguistics, Anthropology, Speech Communication, Social interdisciplinary work of scientists in the fields of psychology, education, literature and other disciplines is considered. Many researchers primarily consider language use to be gender-based. They have been involved in documenting models, but language learning in this field is gendered and many in whose relations one can see the social and political aspects covered. The tension between these two perspectives emerged in early research and continues to be, for example, Preisler (1998) and Cameron (1999) is evidence of exchanges between. Regardless of the perspective from which the research originates, looking at gender and speech studies provide not only descriptive data of male/female speech, rather, language is symbolic for creating and managing personal, social, and cultural meanings also shows how it works as a resource and identities. As our understanding of the relationship between language and gender deepens, researchers have many similar, often unrecognized or recognized variations come to conclusions. The most accepted principles that appear in this article.

The implicit relationship between gender and discourse Tannen (1994c) draws on Goffman (1977) to argue that discourse and gender are unrelated to gender, but claims that "gender is related to class." That is, speech methods to every man or woman not specific, but a class of women or men in a given society (Russell's logical types in the sense of) related to. Speaking in ways associated

with one or another gender category, people indicate that they fit into that gender class. A similar theoretical perspective view is presented by Ochs (1992), which discourse methods are known in turn that it is related to the positions associated with women or men in a culture emphasizes. Thus, speech patterns "indexed gender". Since the connection between gender and speech is indirect, people of gender may not know the effect on speech style. For example, Johnston (1995) four prominent Texans in the conversation with the women, the women proudly admitted that they were from Texas, but denied that their behavior depends on gender. However, in their capacity as lawyers When talking about success, one woman (among other things): "I have to smile I try to keep myself free." Tannen's (1994c: 216) points out that, as Goffman (1976) has shown, it is the way a woman smiles - gender related to the class.

Gender discourse as a resource Constructivist approach assumptions or ideologies and actual discursive practices includes the difference between In other words, "gender speech styles exists independently of the speaker" (Bucholtz and Hall 1995: 7), hence gender discourse serves as a source for self-expression of women and men. As Tannen (1989b: 80) explains, cultural influences on how a speaker's speech does not determine whether; Instead, they are "people expressing their personal style provide a range from which to choose the strategies they typically use." Hall (1995) shows that those who engage in gendered communication over the phone are their to create the gender identity necessary for economic gain in their occupations use gender discourse as a resource, using "women's language". they are "female" use words (lacy) and non-primary color terms (charcoal rather than black) (as described in Lakoff 1975); they use "dynamic" intonation, they are relatively It is characterized by a wide tone range and a clear and rapid shift of tone (McConnell-Ginet 1978); and they actively interact through supportive questions and comments continue (Fishman 1983)

Summary Studies on language and gender are more and more gender and discourse studies is becoming (although variation studies such as Eckert 1989, 1998 quantitative and qualitative although it shows a promising symbiotic relationship between the methods). Language within a specific activity learning-oriented language strategies and culturally determined gender reflects the importance of meanings. It is the creation of gender identities of individuals agency, including resistance to sociocultural norms for language behavior and recognizes the potential for disruption. But it is also the language of women and men the socio-cultural constraints that make their choices and the impact of

these constraints, admit that they will adhere to them or renounce them. In a sense, gender and the field of discourse has come full circle and by Brown, Goodwin, Lakoff and Goffman himself to a constructivist framework influenced by Goffman, as seen in his innovative work returned.

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